

TEETHERS EFFECT ON ORAL HEALTH IN INFANTS

Petrova A.M.,*PhD of Medicine, Head of Pediatric Dentistry Department, Chita State Academy of Medicine***Malezhik M.S.,***PhD of Medicine, Associate Professor of Pediatric Dentistry Department, Chita State Academy of Medicine***Zhilyaeva O.A.,***PhD of Cultural Sciences, Associate Professor of Foreign Languages Department, Chita State Academy of Medicine***Pronin M.Yu.,***Assistant of Pediatric Dentistry Department, Chita State Academy of Medicine***Kucheryavenko E. Yu.***Post graduate of Pediatric Dentistry Department, Chita State Academy of Medicine***Abstract**

All children have an anxious period of infancy when their teeth begin to cut. The eruption of milk teeth is rather often poorly tolerated, brings troubles and unpleasant sensations not only to the child, but also to his parents. The kid usually feels pain, experiences insomniuous nights, often cries, and refuses to eat. Parents are clearly worried about this behavior. A teether is just an effective device which helps to relieve this unpleasant condition, reduce itching, soreness of the gingivae. But the problem lies not only in the selection of a suitable teether, but also in the hygienic state maintaining of such devices.

Keywords: teeth, pain, questionnaire, teether.

Parents are faced with the need to purchase a suitable teether already in the first months of the child's life. Many of them are surprised to worry about the teether so early. But according to the recommendations of many dentists, a teether may be required from this early age. Cutting of temporary teeth in infants is a physiological process. However, it is often accompanied by unpleasant symptoms, such as anxiety of the child, sleep disturbance, leading to a change in the usual lifestyle. To alleviate the child's condition, many parents use teethers that perform several functions at once: provide massage of inflamed gums, thereby reducing itching and soreness; cool the inflamed areas of the oral cavity, thus also reducing pain and edema (provided that a cooled teether is used); switch the attention of the child from unpleasant sensations in the mouth to the teething itself and interaction with it; mediated development of fine motor skills.

Objective: to study the effect of the hygienic state of teethers on the state of the oral cavity in infants.

Tasks:

1. Study scientific information about the etiological factors of caries and diseases of the oral mucosa in infants.
2. Conducting a survey of parents in order to study their level of awareness in matters of hygienic treatment of teethers.
3. Retrospective analysis of the data obtained after the survey.
4. Sanitary and educational work with parents of children.

Materials and methods.

The study of the information obtained on the etiological factors of caries and DMOC (diseases of the mucosa of the oral cavity) in children was carried out with Internet resources. A survey was conducted for parents of children who were being treated in CDDC (Children Department of Dental Clinic) No. 1 of the

Chita State Medical Academy (ChSMA). In total, 100 questionnaires were retrospectively analyzed, which were completed by parents of infants undergoing therapeutic treatment at the CDDC No. 1 of the ChSMA over the past 6 months. Sanitary and educational work was carried out using visual aids.

Background.

Teethers, in their modern sense, appeared relatively recently, but it was rodents for a child that have been used since time immemorial. They were not made then of rubber, plastic or silicone, but of more familiar materials at the time: fabric or wood. Juniper rodents were especially popular. Our ancestors knew about its medicinal properties and, on top of that, the pleasant aroma always came "to the taste" of the child. They also gave a piece of unsalted lard which baby would not gnaw without teeth, but the effect was obvious from constant massage and a soft delicate structure: the child was distracted and calmed down. But gnawing crackers was allowed only to older children, since a dry and rigid structure could only harm the baby, and not alleviate its condition.

According to the material of manufacture, teethers are divided into:

– silicone ones which are considered the most popular and safe for crumbs. There is no taste, and the elastic structure prevents deformation or the ability to bite off part of the accessory. They not lose shape when boiling and are suitable for all known types of sterilizers;

– latex, rubber or gum elastic teethers are less practical to operate, because unlike silicone, they have a softer structure and are more demanding to care for: they cannot be boiled and washed only with a soft soap sponge in warm water. There is also a non-sharp specific taste, which may not appeal to the child. Basically, latex teethers are chosen for its elastic and pliable structure and are used for children up to 6 months until the

first teeth are cut. And then they switch to other stronger materials;

- plastic teethingers are distinguished by strength and safety, and therefore the baby is unlikely to break off a piece. The material has a high density and can take on various shapes, does not require special care conditions: most models can be processed in sterilizers;

- wooden ones are made from juniper, beech or maple. Birch and linden are less preferable, as they have a soft structure, and a piece or chip in the process can break away from the accessory and harm the health of the crumbs. In most cases, the color has a natural hue, which is mainly in the choice. In care, products are demanding and difficult to clean, and therefore require frequent replacement;

- textile teethingers has the property of absorbing saliva, which is already in excess during the eruption period. They are not demanding in care. They have funny shapes and are rarely found in the same type, often there are small plastic or silicone inserts used to massage the gums.

To choose the right option, you need to have an idea of the entire assortment offered. Manufacturers make them taking into account the sequence and peculiarities of cutting. By types, teethingers are divided into models: for cutters located at the top and bottom; for upper and lower canines, as well as for the first indigenous; for distal molars; universal models.

They carry designations according to the stage of tooth growth - I, II and III, respectively. All necessary and useful information is printed on the package.

Choosing a suitable teether, unfortunately, parents often do not think about the hygienic state of such devices, which can lead to the development of diseases of the child's oral cavity. In this regard, the problem of parental awareness is relevant not only in matters of use, but also in maintaining the hygienic state of teethingers.

Discussion.

Most literature sources support evidence that the main ethical factors of oral diseases in children are caused by a microbial factor, and a violation of oral hygiene.

The survey of infants parents revealed the following data: to the question "Do you know what teethingers (rodents) are?" 100% of respondents answered "YES," and 100% of respondents used them during eruption of teeth in a child. Most parents used silicone rodents with a filler in the form of gel or water as a teether, 11% of parents used rattles and other toys.

When asked about the timing of teething use, 65% of parents chose the "3 months" option, 15% answered "6 months" and 20% of parents made teething replacements as they wore out.

Hygienic treatment of rodents was carried out by all respondents, and 100% of the surveyed parents also believe that the treatment was carried out according to the standard. At the same time, hygienic treatment by boiling was carried out by 60% of parents, treatment with antiseptic solutions - 20%, rinsing in running water - 5%, soaking in soap solution - 15% of respondents. More than half (65%) of parents believed that there was a relationship between the hygienic state of the teeth

cutting and diseases of the child's oral cavity, 35% found it difficult to answer this question.

To the question "What diseases can occur with improper and/or insufficient hygienic treatment of teething?" 15% chose the answer option "tooth decay" and 85% chose "diseases of the oral mucosa (stomatitis, etc.)."

During the teething period, 37% of the children whose parents were surveyed experienced diseases of the oral mucosa.

Based on the obtained data, studied scientific information, a relationship was established between the hygienic state of teething and diseases of the oral mucosa in infants. Improper and/or inadequate hygienic treatment of rodents is one of the etiological factors for the development of stomatitis in infants.

After the survey, sanitary and educational work was carried out with the parents: a conversation, demonstration and development of manual skills for the complete and high-quality processing of rodents. Brochures with recommendations were issued with the rules for using teethingers. Hygienic treatment of teethingers involves soaking in solution using a detergent washing gel for 5-7 minutes and washing under running water for 3-5 minutes. Children have diseases of the oral mucosa (stomatitis, etc.) during the use of the teething, before soaking the teething, it is necessary to wipe them 3 times with an alcohol napkin. And it is necessary to follow the expiry date of teethingers: replacement shall be carried out as worn out (with active use). In case of rare use, teethingers are replaced 3 months after the first use.

Conclusion.

The process of the appearance of teeth in baby is inextricably linked with anxiety, pain and, as a result, sleepless nights. The first teeth are hard to give not only to children, but also to adults. Therefore, parents are looking for various options to alleviate the suffering of their children. Using medicines and special gels is an extreme measure. But teethingers are a lifesaver for everyone. If hygiene standards are observed, the teethingers are safe and will not harm a small member of a family.

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